

ISic1361

I.Sicily inscription 1361

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di

Catania, inventory 262

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Ὁ κύριός μου Εὐ
2. ἄγριος ἐχαρίσατό
3. μοι τὸν τόπον ἐμοῖ
4. θεοδούλῳ καὶ κῖντε
5. Κωστάντις καὶ Κεκί
6. λία

Apparatus

Korhonen 2004

Translation (en)

My lord Euagrios, he freely gave this place to me, for me Theodoulos, and here lies Kostantis and Kekilia.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492975

EDCS 39101741

PHI 140865

PHI 316265

Bibliography

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